

Using a Genetic Algorithm for Multi-Hypothesis Tracking

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Abstract

A technique has been devised that uses a genetic algorithm (GA) to address the multi-scan assignment problem in multi-target tracking. The problem is recast in the form of a scheduling problem, where the GA searches the space of possible orderings of detections, and a greedy heuristic is used to make the associations for a particular ordering. The resulting tracker can operate in either batch or continuous mode. In the continuous mode, a single population of hypotheses evolves on a fitness landscape that changes with each new scan of data.

1: Introduction

In a typical multi-target tracking application, a tracker receives a stream of reports over time from one or more sensors (such as a radar), each of which may indicate either the detection of an actual object of interest (or closely spaced group of such objects) or a false alarm. The objects of interest may include, for example, aircraft, missiles, ships, or land vehicles. The tracker may also be used to track particular points on an object (such as an organ in medical imaging applications).

The problem of assigning reports is to determine which reports correspond to which objects. A tracker may deal with many reports collected across some time period (which may be long enough that each real object may have generated two or more reports from observations at different times). Under these circumstances, the number of different ways of combining reports into tracks (or tracks and false alarms) can grow exponentially. Each possible combination is called a hypothesis.

The problem of assigning reports involves searching for an optimal or near-optimal hypothesis according to a metric specific to the tracker in question. In the general case, it is impractical to find the optimal hypothesis for more than a small number of objects observed over time, because of the high computational expense required. Therefore, suboptimal search techniques are usually employed.

Without loss of generality, we may describe the problem of assigning reports as if the sensor reports arrived in groups where each report in the group was collected over the same time period (called a "scan"). The problem of searching for an optimal or near-optimal hypothesis across multiple scans is different in character from searching for the best hypothesis for the associations between reports from one scan and a set of tracks. In general, finding the local optimal assignment of objects (targets) to tracks for each scan does not guarantee that the global assignment across many scans is optimal.

Multi-scan, multiple-target algorithms commonly used include multi-hypothesis trackers (MHTs) [1–3], joint probabilistic data association (JPDA) [3], artificial neural networks [4], integer programming [5], Lagrangian relaxation algorithms [6], and simulated annealing [7,8]. Angus et al [9] and Carrier et al [10] have described methods for using genetic algorithms (GAs) for data association within a single scan.

I describe how a GA using an order-based representation can be applied to the multi-scan data association problem. (I have developed a similar tracker that uses a GA with an edge-based representation and have tested it, in simulation, against other algorithms; the results are described elsewhere [11].) In this paper, the emphasis is on describing a range of configurations for a GA-based tracker, rather than characterizing the performance of any particular one.

2: Single-Hypothesis Tracker

Figure 1 shows a simple scenario in which three detections are reported in scan 0 and two detections in scan 1. At scan 0, there is only one possible hypothesis: each of the three detections represents the start of a new track. At scan 1, there are 13 possible hypotheses under the model described above (including the hypothesis where no detections are associated). All are continuations of the single hypothesis from scan one. Six hypotheses contain three tracks (both new detections are associated with one of the three original tracks), six contain four tracks (one detection is associated with an existing track and one is the start of a new track), and one (with no detections associated) has five tracks. Figure 1 shows three of the 13 hypotheses.

The single-hypothesis tracker must calculate the cost of some or all of the possible hypotheses, at scan 1, and choose one. For purposes of discussion, assume that all 13 hypotheses are tested, and that the hypothesis in figure 1a has the lowest cost and is selected. Figure 2 shows the same scenario with two more detections reported at scan 2. The hypothesis shown in figure 2 cannot be reached, even though it may have the lowest cost, because the tracker is constrained to look only at hypotheses containing the associations of figure 1a.

3: Multiple Hypothesis Tracker

An MHT operates roughly as follows [1–3]. For the first scan, in figure 1, there is only one possible hypothesis, and none of the detections can be associated with any other; thus the hypothesis contains three tracks with one detection each. With the next scan of data, there are 13 possible hypotheses. The tracker calculates and saves all of them, declares the lowest cost hypothesis as the (tentative) winner, and continues. With the third scan of data, the MHT calculates and saves all the hypotheses that can be formed as extensions of each of the 13 previously saved hypotheses.

Figure 1. Some of possible hypotheses for a simple scenario with five detections in 2 scans. $D_{i,j}$ indicates j th detection in scan i , circles represent detections, and arrows indicate associations between them.

Figure 2. A single hypothesis (extension of hypothesis in figure 1c) for same scenario with one more scan.

If left unchecked, as more scans are added, the number of tracks and hypotheses will very quickly expand beyond the resources of processing time or memory available. Some method of “pruning out” the most expendable hypotheses must be regularly applied. One method is to periodically eliminate the highest cost hypotheses until only a predetermined number of hypotheses remain. If a track does not belong to any remaining hypothesis, it is eliminated as well.

For example, assume that the maximum number of hypotheses allowed is three, with no limit on tracks. The tracker builds and evaluates all 13 hypotheses. The three hypotheses shown in figure 1 have the lowest costs and are retained, while the other hypotheses are pruned away. The tracker declares the hypothesis in figure 1a to be the best at that time.

With the new detections from scan 2, the tracker calculates all the possible hypotheses that are continuations of the three remaining hypotheses (shown in figure 1). The hypothesis shown in figure 2 is among those tested and is selected as the best. It and two other hypotheses are retained, while the others are pruned away. For the hypothesis of figure 2 to be true at scan 2, the hypothesis of figure 1c must have been true at scan 1. Thus the tracker has “changed its mind” about the best hypothesis at scan 1.

If, however, the hypothesis in figure 1c were not one of the three best at scan 1, it would have been pruned away, and the hypothesis of figure 2 would never be examined at scan 2.

4: Genetic Algorithm

A genetic algorithm is an artificial intelligence technique based loosely on the process of natural selection in evolutionary biology [12–14]. It has wide applications in optimization, intelligent search, and machine learning.

To apply a GA, one generally expresses the problem in such a way that potential solutions can be encoded as character strings over some alphabet. (Most commonly, these are binary strings, but other representations can be applied.) Then, a population of potential solutions (called “individuals”) is formed. Each individual is decoded, tested against some metric, and scored. A new population is then formed by mutation (small random changes) and recombination (formation of a new individual out of material from a pair of parent individuals). Individuals with relatively high scores or fitnesses are more likely to be selected, as parents, than others. The new population is then decoded and scored, and the process repeated until some end condition is reached.

4.1: Implementation

The GA developed for this tracker uses order-based strings, described below. Similar implementations are

found in the literature, sometimes applied to scheduling, traveling salesman, or graph partitioning problems [13–17]. It uses the “elite” model and has nonoverlapping generations: at each generation the new population completely replaces the old, except for the best individual, which lives on.

Each individual is a string of integers in the form of a permutation of length N . Mutation consists of taking a random point in the string and moving it to a random location. In crossover, parts of two parents are combined to form two children. To be valid individuals, the children must also be permutations. A random crosspoint on the string is chosen, and all points before it are copied over from the first parent into the first child. All points in the second parent whose values do not already exist in the child are copied into the remaining half of the child, in the order in which they are found in the second parent. For the second child, the roles of the two parents are reversed.

For example, given parent1 = [1 2 3 4 5 6], parent2 = [3 4 1 2 6 5], and a crosspoint between the third and fourth points, we can determine the structure of the children:

The first part of child1 = [1 2 3]. The remaining numbers (4, 5, and 6) are in the order 4, ... 6, 5 in the second parent. So child1 = [1 2 3 4 6 5]. The first part of the child2 = [3 4 1]. The remaining numbers (2, 5, and 6) are in the order 2, ... 5, 6 in the second parent. So child2 = [3 4 1 2 5 6].

5: Genetic Algorithm Tracker

The tracker is of the batch-processing class [1,3]: it uses an optimizing algorithm, a GA, to search for the best hypothesis over a window of time, S scans deep. By applying the search across multiple windows, it produces a hypothesis for all the detections.

5.1: Search Across One Window

A single fixed hypothesis holds the track estimates up to the start of the current window. This hypothesis, the “starting hypothesis,” cannot be changed during the search. The GA searches the space of extensions of this fixed hypothesis across the window. To search across this window, the tracker forms hypotheses by taking each detection in order and assigning it to the track (possibly a new track) that produces the best association (lowest cost) available for that detection. The GA searches for the best order in which to process the detections.

The process starts by creating a population of M randomly generated individuals. An individual is encoded as a permutation of the N sensor detections reported in the window. Each individual is then decoded and scored by being run through the decoding module, which uses a greedy heuristic to produce a hypothesis.

Every hypothesis inherits the associations in the starting hypothesis, so every hypothesis (implicitly) includes an association for every detection from the beginning of time. The cost of the starting hypothesis is also inherited.

The decoding module could serve as a crude single-hypothesis tracker itself. As each point is received (in the order described by the individual), the module calculates the cost of associating that detection with each of the active tracks that it has already formed for that individual (including those inherited from the starting hypothesis), as well as the cost of assigning the detection as a new track. (Track associations that would require a target to move backwards in time, occupy two places at once, or violate other constraints are given prohibitively high costs.) The lowest cost option is taken; the track’s state is updated by a track filter such as those described by Blackman [2] (in this case, an alpha/beta filter is used for simplicity); and the next detection is considered until all points have been assigned. The fitness of the individual is inversely related to the cost of the resulting hypothesis: in this case, the sum of the costs of the associations made for each detection.

It is worth noting that there is no restriction on how the cost of a hypothesis is calculated, other than that it must be a nonnegative function of all the associations encountered, including those before the present window. It might be desirable in this example, for instance, to add a cost term for tracks not updated in a scan to account for the probability of detection.

With this model, the hypothesis in figure 1a could be encoded by the string $[D_{0,0} D_{1,0} D_{0,1} D_{1,1} D_{0,2}]$. The hypothesis in figure 2 could be encoded by the string $[D_{0,1} D_{1,0} D_{2,0} D_{0,2} D_{1,1} D_{2,1} D_{0,0}]$.

The mapping of strings to hypotheses is not one to one. Strings with detections in different orders may or may not decode into different hypotheses, depending on whether the detections could be associated with the same tracks.

At the end of the time available, the best solution found so far is used to construct a new “best” hypothesis for all the detections up to the end of the window. If the GA has a population size of M and runs for T generations, the number of hypotheses tested will be the product of M and T . Because a GA naturally produces exact copies of some individuals, and because different permutations of detections may decode into identical hypotheses, the number of unique hypotheses tested will be lower.

The above treatment has a weakness that is illustrated by the simple example of a single target detected on each of S scans in the window. The association problem should be solved trivially by association of all the N detections (in this case, $N = S$) into a single track. But there is only one of $N!$ permutations that can be decoded to produce this result. Using randomly formed permutations as the starting popu-

lation for the GA is extremely inefficient, especially for large S .

The “random” permutations discussed in this paper are actually biased so that the detections are more likely to be listed in time order, from earliest to latest. One method of forming such a biased initial population is to form each individual as a random permutation of the detections in the first scan, followed by a random permutation of the detections in the second scan, and so on. These individuals are then subjected to several iterations of the mutation operator, described above, to provide some mixing between scans.

5.2: Continuous Tracking

The above section describes how a GA can search for a low-cost hypothesis across a single window S scans deep. Many typical tracker applications require the calculation of a best hypothesis after each scan of data for an indefinite number of scans. A tracker program could be created to produce periodic updates to the best hypothesis by invoking the search across one window every S scans and using the best hypothesis of the previous window as the starting hypothesis of the new window. Since these windows would not overlap, such a tracker would produce an undesirable bottleneck every S scans, by reducing the number of hypotheses carried forward to one. An additional drawback is that this tracker would not produce a hypothesis after receiving each scan of data.

5.2.1: Siding Window. An alternative approach would be to use a sliding window. A starting hypothesis holds the hypothesis (track estimates) up to the start of the window. The GA searches the space of extensions of this fixed hypothesis across the window (but does not modify the starting hypothesis). At the end of the time available, the best solution found so far is used to construct a new fixed hypothesis, one scan further in time from the beginning. The window slides forward to include the next scan of data. The new window overlaps the old, offset by one scan. The GA is called again to find the best hypothesis (with the new fixed hypothesis as its starting hypothesis) for the new window, and the process continues.

The siding window approach can be illustrated by the following example, in which a window size of five scans is used. When the tracker is first turned on, there are no prior points to consider, there are no points in the window, and there is nothing for the tracker to do. At some scan in the future, scan 0, some points are reported. A population is formed from random permutations. Each individual is decoded into a hypothesis and scored. In our simple model, since all the points have time tags from the same scan, none of the points is allowed to associate with any point

other than itself, in which case the population represents many identical hypotheses in which all points are the start of new tracks. The GA is called to operate on the population until some stopping criterion is reached. (Typical stopping criteria might include the completion of a fixed number of generations, the difference in fitness between the fittest individual and the average for the population falling below a threshold, or an interrupt signalling the arrival of a new scan of data.) The hypothesis of the fittest individual is reported as the hypothesis for that scan (although later hypotheses could, in principle, amend it, based on additional data). If the next scan contains more reports, then a new population is formed from random permutations of all the points in the window. This new population is operated on by the GA once more.

After five scans, the window is full and must slide forward to include the next scan. The individual with the highest score (the best hypothesis at scan 4) is used to calculate the fixed hypothesis for scan 0. The fixed hypothesis for scan 0 is constructed from the assignments in the best hypothesis for points with times before the end of scan 1. This hypothesis will be the “starting hypothesis” for scan 0.

This individual has the highest score for scan 4 but may or may not have the hypothesis with the highest score at scan 0. The starting hypothesis for scan 0 may be different from the original hypothesis reported by the tracker and may in fact have a worse score at scan 0. The possibility that selecting a hypothesis with a relatively poor score at an early scan may lead to a hypothesis with a better score at a later scan is the reason for performing multi-scan optimization.

The new points from scan 5 are then added to the window containing the reports from scans 1 to 4, and the GA is invoked once more. While the associations for points before the start of the window may not be changed, points within the window may have associations with points outside.

The tracker continues in this manner indefinitely. The strings of the individuals will be longer or shorter from one window to the next, depending on how many points were generated over the scans in the window. At the start of each new scan, the tracker produces an output hypothesis for all the detections before that scan, which may or may not amend some of the associations in hypotheses output at previous scans.

This approach has the advantage that the bottleneck of a single unchangeable hypothesis is made $S - 1$ scans in the past and is therefore more likely to be correct. It has the disadvantage that it requires S times as much computation as the nonoverlapping technique. A more serious disadvantage is that, when the new fixed hypothesis is used to start a new window, it might be impossible to recreate the win-

ning hypothesis that gave rise to it in the first place. There might be no permutation of the remaining detections (plus those from the next scan) that can result in the original associations.

5.2.2: Overlapping Windows. An alternative approach is similar to the sliding window, except that the starting hypothesis for a window is chosen to be the hypothesis with the lowest cost, for that time, found by the program. While this choice might appear, at first, to result in the equivalent of a single-hypothesis tracker, it does not, because the lowest cost hypothesis for scan K is not constrained to have the same associations for the same points as the lowest cost hypothesis for scan $K - 1$.

As the program is forming and evaluating each hypothesis for all the points in the window, it is simultaneously calculating the cost for S subhypotheses: the subset of the hypothesis' associations up to the end of each scan within the window. These costs include the cost inherited from the window's starting hypothesis. If one of the subhypotheses evaluated results in the lowest cost encountered for that scan for any of the scans within the window, then that subhypothesis (including all the associations inherited from its starting hypothesis) is saved as the tentative starting hypothesis.

5.3: GA Multi-Hypothesis Tracker

Only a few changes are needed to transform the batch mode tracker described above into a continuous mode tracker analogous to an MHT. When a new scan of data arrives, instead of the GA being restarted, the strings of the individuals in the existing population are extended by a random permutation of the new detections being appended to the end of them; the process of decoding and scoring of hypotheses and forming successive generations by crossover and mutation continues uninterrupted.

The process can be visualized as one in which the window size is infinite, and the lengths of the individual's strings grow forever, but the crossover and mutation operators are forced to pick points within N points of the end. Since manipulating and decoding these ever-growing strings would quickly prove impractical, some shortcuts are employed. Each new individual formed by the GA will inherit all but the last N detections of its string, intact, from one of its parents. This string of ordered detections can be decoded into a hypothesis (set of tracks) just once, and they can be included by reference thereafter.

The GA still operates across a sliding window, but the window is based on number of detections, not time, and each individual includes its own starting hypothesis. The crossover operator is still constrained to pick a crossover point within a sliding window equal to the number of de-

tections in the last S scans, and the mutation operator is still constrained to pick a detection within the window and move it to a location that is also within the window. However, the hypotheses are not constrained to have the same associations for detections before the start of the window.

When a new scan of data containing D detections arrives, the starting hypothesis and the first D detections for each individual are decoded to produce a new starting hypothesis (including a state for all tracks) for that individual. The number of starting hypotheses is equal to the number of individuals in the population. The D detections are removed from the front of the individuals' strings, shortening them. (The ordering of the detections is not lost, because it is included in the new starting hypothesis.) The string for each individual is then extended by the addition of a random permutation of the new detections onto the end. The mutation operator will mix these detections with those from other scans during subsequent generations.

Each individual is encoded as an ordered list of detections plus a number (pointer) indicating which starting hypothesis it owns. When a new individual is formed, it inherits a pointer to the starting hypothesis of one of its parents. This tracker is similar to a traditional MHT, in that the starting hypotheses form a pool of hypotheses that can theoretically contain different associations for detections that are arbitrarily far back in time.

GA applications typically require some care to prevent premature convergence. The GA tracker is somewhat unusual in that it should never converge. Each new scan of detections changes not only the fitness landscape on which the GA must operate, but the lengths of the strings as well.

6: Complexity

The quality of the solutions found by a GA-based tracker can be improved if we increase the number of scans in the window, the size of the population, and the number of generations. Analogous gains may be obtained from most multi-scan algorithms, also at the cost of increased processing time.

Table 1 shows the results of increasing the window size, for a simulated data set (also used in Winkler et al [11]), for a GA tracker with overlapping windows. There are 16 maneuvering targets observed over 30 scans. For each window, the population size is, dynamically, set to be equal to N , where N is the number of detections occurring within the window. The number of generations, per window, is also set to be N , so that N^2 hypotheses are examined for each window. Since the decoding module has a processing cost that is proportional to N^2 , the complexity of this particular implementation should be on the order of N^4 . The memory requirements grow only as the square of N .

Table 1. Performance of a GA tracker using overlapping windows for different window sizes (in scans). Results from 10 independent trials for each window size.

Window size	Avg. cost
1	26087
2	24972
3	24389
4	23493

The cost obtained by use of the Munkres algorithm (a single-hypothesis algorithm described in Blackman [2]) was 25530. The GA has a relatively poor performance with a window size of one scan, but improves with larger windows.

7: Discussion

The GA based approach has a number of attractive features:

1. GAs (and hybrids between GAs and other algorithms such as local search techniques and simulated annealing) have been used successfully in a number of similar problem domains [15–23].

2. GAs can be very efficiently implemented on parallel processors via an island model with a subpopulation on each processor [13], or a parallel GA [15] where each individual interacts asynchronously with only a few neighbors. Such parallel implementations can be highly scalable, so that the number of processors can be changed without the need for significant modification to the code.

3. The performance vs. computation trade-off can be adjusted smoothly by changes in the depth of the window, the size of the population, and the number of generations. These changes can be made adaptively during run time.

4. After the first generation, the search process may be interrupted at any time and the best hypothesis found so far will be available. This leads to graceful degradation.

8: References

1. D. B. Reid, "An Algorithm for Tracking Multiple Targets," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control* **AC-24** (December 1979), 843–854.
2. S. Blackman, "Multiple Target Tracking with Radar Applications" (Artech House, Dedham, MA, 1986).
3. Y. Bar-Shalom, ed., "Multitarget-Multisensor Tracking: Applications and Advances," Vol. II (Artech House, MA, 1992).
4. S. Shams, "Neural Network Optimization for Multi-Target Multi-Sensor Passive Tracking," *Proc. IEE* **84**, No. 10 (October 1996), 1442–1457.
5. C. Morefield, "Application of 0-1 Integer Programming to Multitarget Tracking Problems," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control* **AC-22** No. 3 (June 1977), 302–312.
6. K. Pattipati, S. Deb, Y. Bar-Shalom, and R. Washburn, "A New Relaxation Algorithm and Passive Sensor Data Association," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control* **AC-37** (1992), 198–213.
7. P. Ting and R. Iltis, "Multi-target Motion Analysis in a DSN," *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.* **21** (1991), 1125–1139.
8. R. Iltis and K. Anderson, "A Consistent Estimation Criterion for Multi-Sensor Bearings-Only Tracking," *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.* **32** (January 1996), 108–120.
9. J. Angus, H. Zhou, C. Bea, L. Becket-Lemus, J. Klose, and S. Tubbs, "Genetic Algorithms in Passive Tracking," Claremont Grad. School, Math Clinic Rep. (May 1993).
10. J. Carrier, J. Litva, H. Leung, and T. To, "Genetic Algorithm for Multiple Target Tracking Data Association," *Proc. SPIE 2739, Acquisition, Tracking and Pointing*, 180–190 (April 1996).
11. R. Winkler, P. David, and D. Hillis, "An Empirical Comparison of the Accuracy of Data Association Algorithms for Multi-Target Tracking," 19th Army Science Conference (June 1994).
12. J. Holland, "Adaptation in Natural and Artificial Systems" (University of Michigan Press, 1975).
13. D. Goldberg, "Genetic Algorithms in Search, Optimization, and Machine Learning" (Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA, 1989).
14. Z. Michalkawicz, "Genetic Algorithms + Data Structures = Evolution Programs" (Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1992).
15. N. Ulder, E. Aarts, H. Bandelt, P. van Laarhoven, and E. Pech, "Genetic Local Search Algorithms for the Traveling Salesman," *Parallel Problem Solving from Nature*, 1st Workshop (Springer-Verlag, Oct. 1990), 109–116.
16. H. C. Braun, "On Solving Travelling Salesman Problems by Genetic Algorithms," *Parallel Problem Solving from Nature*, 1st Workshop (Springer-Verlag, Oct. 1990), 129–133.
17. G. von Lawszewski and H. Muhlenbein, "Partitioning a Graph with a Parallel Genetic Algorithm," *Parallel Problem Solving from Nature*, 1st Workshop (Springer-Verlag, Oct. 1990), 165–169.
18. G. Lawton, "Genetic Algorithms for Schedule Optimization," *AI Expert*, (May 1992), 23–27.
19. S. Ucken, S. Bagchi, and K. Kawamura, "Managing Genetic Search in Job Shop Scheduling," *IEEE Expert* **8**, Issue 5, (October 1993), 15–24.
20. K. Maekawa, N. Mori, H. Tamaki, H. Kita, and Y. Nishikawa, "A Genetic Solution for the Traveling Salesman Problem by Means of a Thermodynamical Selection Rule," *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Evolutionary Computation* (1996), 529–53.
21. K. Wong and Y. Wong, "Combined Genetic Algorithm/Simulated Annealing/Fuzzy Set Approach to Short-Term Generation Scheduling with Take-Or-Pay Fuel Contract," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* **11** (1996), 128–136.
22. T. Murata, H. Tshibuchi, "Performance Evaluation of Genetic Algorithms for Flowshop Scheduling Problems," *Proc. First IEEE Conference on Evolutionary Computation. IEEE World Congress on Computational Intelligence* (1994), 812–817.
23. C. Holsapple, V. Jacob, R. Pakath, and J. Zaveri, "A Genetics-Based Hybrid Scheduler for Generating Static Schedules in Flexible Manufacturing Contexts," *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.* **23** (1993), 953–972.